

NONDESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION OF COMPOSITES BY
ELASTIC WAVE PROPAGATION ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Ultrasonic inspection is the most favorable method for detection of defects in composites, and delaminations, voids, porosity, and lack of bonding are detected by various ultrasonic techniques, such as through-transmission scanning, pulse-echo, thickness gaging and resonance impedance. However, defects concerning fibers, such as fiber breakage and impact damage are not effectively detected. This paper proposes a new system to evaluate these defects by analyzing elastic wave propagation in composites. In this system, longitudinal wave is introduced into the specimen by a probe which is specially made for FRP. The measured wave signals are Fourier transformed into frequency spectrum data and evaluation parameters are calculated. Two types of model defects in unidirectional CFRP were detected, which were (1) concentrated type, that is, one hole is located in the middle of specimen, and (2) dispersed type, that is, some holes were dispersed around the specimen. The size and type of these defects were successfully evaluated by the parameter. Dynamic simulations on elastic wave propagation in composites are also carried out, which show the reflection, refraction and mode transition of elastic wave in detail. The evaluations of defects in composites are successfully simulated on each types of specimen, which clearly explains the experimental results.

KEYWORDS: Nondestructive testing; Ultrasonic; Wave propagation; Unidirectional; Carbon/Epoxy composites.

1. INTRODUCTION

From a microscopic point of view, composites generally contain innumerable defects in themselves, but even if they have some defects, many of them are sometimes almost harmless depending upon types, locations and applied conditions. On the other hand, in a stress concentrated region, even a very minute defect often causes a crack growth and becomes a fatal

size. So it is very important to evaluate the size and the types of defects in composites precisely. Ultrasonic inspection is said to be the most effective way to solve the problem, but detection of defects in composites is generally more difficult than that of metal because of their heterogeneity and anisotropy. Some types of defects parallel to a lamina, such as fiber break and crack perpendicular to a lamina have been very difficult to detect. Recently, several new techniques to examine frequency spectrum of acquired ultrasonic wave have been devised, and defects which were not detected by conventional ways such as micro-cracks and voids in fine ceramics (1,2) and σ embrittlement of stainless steel (3) have been successfully evaluated. As for composites, some reports have described possibility of detection in similar ways (4), but there have been few experimental results. In this paper, we establish a new system to evaluate defects in composites effectively by analyzing through-transmission waveform and calculating evaluation parameters. Dynamic simulation of wave propagation in unidirectional composites are also carried out in order to examine how waves are affected by the defects.

2. EVALUATION OF DEFECTS IN COMPOSITES

2.1 Setup of Nondestructive Evaluation System

Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram of NDE system. The elastic wave is introduced into the specimen by a high damping type probe which is acoustically in conformity with plastic matrix composites. The center frequency of the probe is 5MHz. The through transmitted wave is picked up by an AE transducer through the acrylic triangular column (width = 10mm) mounted on the specimen at certain distance from the introduced point and routed to the pre-amplifier. The wave signal is recorded by the transient memory and Fourier transformed by the FFT analyzer. A frequency spectrum is obtained by averaging the measured 16 spectra.

Fig.1 Schematic diagram of NDE system.

2.2 Detection of Model Defects in Unidirectional Carbon/Epoxy Composites

Specimens examined are unidirectional carbon/epoxy composites. Two types of model defects illustrated in Fig. 2 are made, which are (1) concentrated-defect type, that is, one hole (diameter = 2, 3, 6, 10 mm) is located at 20mm from the edge, (2) dispersed-defects type, that is, 3, 5 or 10 holes (diameter = 2mm) are dispersed over the range 100 to 200 mm from

(a) Concentrated-defect (b) Dispersed-defects

Fig.2 Evaluated specimen.

the edge. The through-transmitted wave are picked up at 30mm from the introduced edge.

Figure 3 shows the typical received waveforms. In concentrated-defect type, as the diameter of the hole becomes large, amplitude of waves become smaller. Especially, in case of diameter of the hole is 10mm, definite attenuation is observed. Considering the total flaw width of dispersed-defects type specimen which has 5 holes is 10 mm, amplitude of dispersed type is found to be larger than that of concentrated type. However, it is difficult to distinguish these types of defects by examining time-dependent waveforms alone. Figure 4 shows a series of frequency spectra. The most behind data in the figure is the spectrum received at the introducing edge. In case of no defect specimen, there is little difference between the spectrum at the edge and at the picked-up point. Though amplitude of defected specimen is small in all frequency range, amplitude of dispersed type in higher frequency range is larger than that of concentrated type.

Fig.3 Typical received waveforms.

(a) Concentrated-defect

(b) Dispersed-defects

Fig.4 Frequency spectra of received wave.

So as to evaluate these aspects quantitatively, an evaluation parameter is calculated as follows: (1) Correlation between waveform before the defects and after the defects are examined with coherence coefficient and further calculation is carried out in the frequency range where the value is above 0.8. (2) Each frequency spectrum is divided by the spectrum received at the edge, which makes the parameter independent of the effect of coupling, attachment, transducer, and so on. (3) Acquired value, which is a kind of transmission function of the material, is integrated in lower (0 - 2.5 MHz) and higher (2.5 - 5 MHz) frequency range respectively and two evaluation parameters are calculated. Figure 5 shows the size of defects versus evaluation parameter for each type. By comparing parameter of higher frequency range with that of lower range, type of the defects is clearly distinguished; that is, total size of the defects is evaluated by the magnitude of parameters and type of defects is evaluated by the ratio of two parameters.

Fig.5 Evaluation parameters versus the size of defects.

3. SIMULATIONS ON ELASTIC WAVE PROPAGATION

3.1 Establishment of Model In examining defects in composites by means of elastic wave propagation analysis, it is important to know how the waves propagate in the material and how they are affected by the defects. Though some theoretical analyses have been made on the wave propagation in composites (5,6), there are so many types of inherent defects in composites that the general aspects have not been fully clarified. Therefore, we propose a new two-dimensional wave propagation model of a unidirectional fiber reinforced composites, in which many types of defects are easily simulated, and dynamic simulations based on this model are carried out.

Figure 6 shows the simulation model. Nodal points are placed on fibers, which requires a small number of nodal points for the number of elements. The defects of fiber and matrix are assumed to be between two nodal points, which is convenient because the displacement array is

Fig.6 Basic simulation model.

not cognizant of the defect and mass of the element remains unchanged when fibers and matrices are disconnected at the location. A section enclosed with dotted lines is defined as "Composite element", including fiber and matrix. Assuming the stiffness of fiber is much larger than that of matrix, equation of motion of composite element in the x-direction, is:

$$\rho d \delta \frac{\partial^2 u^2}{\partial t^2} = (\lambda_f + 2\mu_f) \delta d_f \frac{\partial^2 u^2}{\partial x^2} + (\lambda_m + \mu_m) \delta d_m \frac{\partial^2 w^2}{\partial x \partial z} + \mu_m \delta d_m \frac{\partial^2 u^2}{\partial z^2} \quad (1)$$

where, u : displacement in the x-direction, w : displacement in the z-direction, ρ : density, d : distance between nodes in the z-direction, d : distance between nodes in the x-direction, λ , μ : Lamé's constants. Subscriptions f , m denote fiber, matrix, respectively. The second order partial differentials in the right side of Eq. (1) are approximated by the difference forms,

$$\frac{\partial^2 u_i^j}{\partial x^2} = \frac{1}{\delta^2} (u_i^{j-1} - 2u_i^j + u_i^{j+1}) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 u_i^j}{\partial z^2} = \frac{1}{d_m^2} (u_{i-1}^j - 2u_i^j + u_{i+1}^j) \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 w_i^j}{\partial x \partial z} = \frac{1}{4\delta d_m} (w_{i+1}^{j+1} - w_{i+1}^{j-1} - w_{i-1}^{j+1} + w_{i-1}^{j-1}) \quad (4)$$

where, the superscript j denotes node number in the x-direction and the subscript i denotes node number in the z-direction. substituting Eq. (2)- (4) into Eq. (1) leads to,

$$\begin{aligned} \rho d \delta \frac{d u_i^j}{dt^2} = & \frac{(\lambda_f + 2\mu_f) V_f}{\delta^2} (u_i^{j-1} - 2u_i^j + u_i^{j+1}) + \frac{\mu_m}{d^2 V_m} (u_{i-1}^j - 2u_i^j + u_{i+1}^j) \\ & + \frac{\lambda_m + \mu_m}{4\delta d} (w_{i+1}^{j+1} - w_{i+1}^{j-1} - w_{i-1}^{j+1} + w_{i-1}^{j-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Similarly, as for in the z-direction,

$$\rho d \delta \frac{d^2 w_1^j}{dt^2} = \frac{\mu_m V_m}{\delta^2} (w_{i-1}^{j-1} - 2w_1^j + w_{i+1}^{j+1}) + \frac{\lambda_m + 2\mu_m}{d^2 V_m} (w_{i-1}^j - 2w_1^j + w_{i+1}^j) + \frac{\lambda_m + \mu_m}{4\delta d} (u_{i+1}^{j+1} - u_{i+1}^{j-1} - u_{i-1}^{j+1} + u_{i-1}^{j-1}) \quad (6)$$

is obtained. From Eq. (5) and Eq. (6), time-dependent nodal displacements are calculated by means of the Newmark's β method ($\beta = 1/4$) with the initial conditions, $u(0) = w(0) = 0$.

Defects of composite are formulated on the assumption that the fiber is always broken at the center of two nodal points as is illustrated in Fig.7. If the fiber is broken between nodal points, N_i^j and N_{i-1}^{j-1} , Eq. (2) and Eq. (4) are replaced by the following equations:

$$\frac{\partial^2 u_1^j}{\partial x^2} = \frac{4}{3\delta^2} (u_{i+1}^{j+1} - u_i^j) \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 w_1^j}{\partial x \partial z} = \frac{1}{4\delta d_m} (w_{i+1}^{j+1} - w_{i-1}^{j+1}) \quad (8)$$

Similarly, the difference forms for N_{i-1}^{j-1} are replaced. In addition, difference forms for N_{i-1}^j , N_{i-1}^{j-1} , N_{i+1}^j and N_{i+1}^{j-1} are replaced such as,

$$\frac{\partial^2 u_{i+1}^j}{\partial x \partial z} = \frac{1}{4\delta d_m} (u_{i+2}^{j+1} - u_{i+2}^{j-1} - u_i^{j+1} + u_{i+1}^j) \quad (9)$$

As for the matrix break, the matrix between two nodal points is assumed to have no stiffness. If the matrix between N_i^j and N_{i+1}^j is broken, Eq.

(3) is replaced with,

$$\frac{\partial^2 u_1^j}{\partial z^2} = \frac{1}{d_m^2} (u_{i-1}^j - u_i^j) \quad (10)$$

Fig.7 Nodes affected by defects of elements.

The other replacements about 6 nodes shown in Fig.6(b) applies correspondingly to the case of fiber break. In case of complex defects of fiber and matrix shown in Fig.6(c), equations for 8 nodes will be replaced.

3.2 Observation of Elastic Wave Propagation

Dynamic simulations are carried out under the condition that one edge of a unidirectional CFRP (in the fiber direction) is fixed and time-dependent force is loaded on the other edge. The numerical values used in the simulation are shown in Table 1. First, wave propagation velocity in the x-direction are examined, when a continuous sine wave force is loaded. The longitudinal wave velocity obtained from simulation, C_p , is 9189 ms^{-1} , and the transverse wave velocity, C_{sv} , is 1289 ms^{-1} .

Table 1 Constants used in simulation.

Lame's constnts	λ_f	132.86	GPa
	λ_m	1.84	
	μ_f	88.58	
	μ_m	1.23	
Density	ρ_f	1.8×10^3	Kgm
	ρ_m	1.1×10^3	
Size of composite element	d	1.55×10^{-5}	m
	δ	8.77×10^{-6}	
Volume fraction	V_f	0.4	

Fig.8 Vector chart of nodal displacements on notched simulation model.

The corresponding theoretical values obtained using the known elastic constants are, $C_p = 8726 \text{ ms}^{-1}$, $C_{SV} = 1213 \text{ ms}^{-1}$, respectively. The values obtained from the simulation and calculated ones appear to agree very well.

Influences of fiber defects on the elastic wave propagation are examined by means of the simulation. Figure 8 shows vector charts after a single sine wave is loaded on the edge of CFRP which has a notched defect, that is, some breakages of the fiber arranged continuously. The notched defect is located in the middle of the composite, which is one-third of the specimen width. First, longitudinal wave, IL propagates in a row, [(a), (b)]. When the wave gets to the notch, reflected wave, RL1 is observed [(d), (e)]; the diffraction wave is also observed, but its amplitude is rather small because of anisotropy. In Fig.8(e), mode conversion to transverse wave at the notch is also observed. The reflective transverse wave, RT, propagates slowly [(f) to (h)]. Two kinds of longitudinal waves, IL and RL, are reflected at each side, respectively [(g)]. The phase of RL2 which is reflected at the fixed edge is shown to be reversed despite RL1' (from the free edge) is not. Interference of two reflection waves RL1' and RL2 are observed in Fig.8(j).

The changes in the time-dependent displacements in the x-direction due to the notch are clearly shown in Fig.9. At the point before the notch, several positive peaks due to the reflection at two free edges appear. At the point after the notch, amplitude due to the diffraction wave is rather small. Figure 10 shows the accelerations versus time at the same point. Similar changes in amplitude and frequency are observed. Therefore, by analyzing the wave propagation in composite, defects of composites can be effectively examined.

(a) Before the notch

(a) Before the notch

(b) After the notch

(b) After the notch

Fig.9 Displacements on the simulation model.

Fig.10 Accelerations on the simulation model.

Fig.11 Vector chart of nodal displacements on simulation model with a hole defect.

Fig.12 Vector chart of nodal displacements on simulation model with dispersed defects.

Figure 11 shows vector charts of CFRP with a hole defect. When the introduced wave arrives at the hole, through transmitted longitudinal wave, IL, and reflected wave, RL are observed just as shown in Fig. 8. The shape of RL, however, is not flat and the received waveform of RL is different from that of the notched specimen. On the other hand, received waveform after the hole is almost same as the notched specimen. So if the parameters obtained from the waveform received after the defects are combined with ones obtained from reflected waveform, more information about the defects can be acquired. Figure 12 shows vector charts of dispersed-defects type specimen. In this type of defects, some small reflected waves are observed, and through transmission wave and diffraction waves are observed in all area even after the defects, which suggests the higher evaluation parameters of this type. By introducing waveform obtained inversely from the experimental frequency spectrum, evaluation parameters are also calculated in the simulation. The result is found to be in good accordance to experimental one.

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we propose a new system to evaluate these defects by analyzing elastic wave propagation in composites. The results are summarized as follows:

- (1) Two types of defects were examined by the evaluation parameter calculated from through transmission waveforms. The size and types of these defects were successfully evaluated by these parameters.
- (2) Dynamic simulations based on a new two-dimensional wave propagation model of a unidirectional fiber reinforced composites were carried out by means of a finite difference scheme.
- (3) The reflection and mode transition of elastic wave at the boundary were visualized in detail, and the influences of defects on the wave propagation were examined. In addition, more parameters to evaluate the defects in composites were suggested.

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